

RESEARCH ON THE CONSTRUCTION OF PUBLIC SERVICE SYSTEM OF ART EDUCATION

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The construction of public service system is an important task of the government, and it is also the key content of China's administrative system reform. The construction of public service system of art education is the key problem to be solved urgently in the development of art education at present. Under this background, this paper analyzes the construction of public service system of art education, and puts forward specific construction strategies, hoping to improve the quality of public service of art education and build a sustainable public service system of art education.

Keywords: art education, public service system, construction, connotation

First, the connotation of art education public service system

The public service system of art education is mainly a series of systems led by the government, with the key task of providing basic and guaranteed public service products and the goal of sharing the fruits of reform and development among members of society. Among them, the most prominent features are government-led, social participation and institutional innovation. Art education has distinct welfare and public welfare, and the government has an important responsibility that cannot be shirked. The construction of public service system of art education must be centered on the government, and the development process should be closely combined with public financial expenditure. However, there are many problems in the development of art education, mainly because the government has not established a strong sense of responsibility, which leads to many problems such as expensive admission and difficult admission. Therefore, the level and efficiency of the construction of public service system for art education also depend on the government's investment and attention. The public service system refers to the comprehensiveness of service objects and the publicity of products, which also determines that the construction of the public service system of art education is mainly led by the government, but it does not mean that the service subject is the government, so it should be the main body of the public service of art education by providing public services of art education or public products and preschool students. The public service system of art education should strengthen the effective input of public finance, and construct the guarantee mechanism of funds input from multiple channels, which will help to ensure the effective improvement of the quality of public service of art education. Art education should be based on the specific requirements in the "National Medium-and Long-term Education Reform and Development Program", closely combine the laws of children's physical and mental development, and adopt many methods such as scientific education protection to promote children's healthy growth. In order to effectively prevent the tendency of primary school education in kindergarten, we should strengthen the unity of quality and quantity in the public service system of art education. Remember not to neglect the

quality of art education in order to improve the popularity of art education, leading to the loss of innocence and freedom of children.

Second, the construction strategy of art education public service system

In order to promote the sustainable development of art education, we must establish the concept of harmonious development, strengthen the effective unity of speed and development quality, scale and connotation, and build a scientific and perfect public service system of art education through gradual advancement. This paper expounds the construction strategy of public service system of art education from the following aspects:

(A) to strengthen children's awareness and establish a child-centered educational concept.

The construction of public service system of art education is a gradual process, in which a child-centered management concept should be established, and the sustainable development of art education can be effectively promoted by popularizing children's awareness. The development of art education belongs to government behavior and administrative behavior. Remember that it cannot be turned into national behavior and mass behavior. We should effectively develop the comprehensiveness, sustainability, effectiveness and scientificity of art education, ensure that the service subject of art education is children, clarify children's awareness, build a scientific and perfect art education service system, and take children as the center to ensure the maximization of children's rights and interests. And the maximization of children's rights and interests has evolved into the mainstream culture of society, which is helpful to ensure the healthy development of children's body and mind and their right to education.

(two) improve the legal system of art education, and effectively ensure the sustainable development of art education.

Due to the lack of relevant laws and regulations on art education, it is difficult to effectively popularize art education. In order to ensure the sustainable development of art education, we should clarify and construct the public service system of art education, strengthen the legislative work of art education, effectively integrate the development of art education into the rule of law and institutionalization, ensure that the development of art education can be based on laws, and effectively strengthen the public financial investment in art

education by clarifying the status and role of art education, politics and the responsibilities of governments and units at all levels, so as to effectively improve the quality of art education and help popularize the development goals of art education.

(C) clear government responsibilities, strengthen public financial input.

Art education belongs to social public welfare undertakings. Without the guidance and help of the government, it is difficult to develop sustainably, so it is necessary to strengthen the financial investment in art education. No matter from the theoretical level or the practical level, we must correctly understand the important role of government investment, which seriously restricts the development of art education. At present, the development of art education in China encourages the diversified social participation of the main body and the socialization development trend of art education, but it does not absolve the government from its responsibility. We should effectively play the role of government propaganda and driving, effectively enhance the effective integration of non-governmental forces, and improve the quality and efficiency of art education. It can be explained that the government is the main body responsible for the development of art education. The government should effectively strengthen public financial input and implement local responsibility and hierarchical management systems. However, because some areas still adopt centralized management, it is necessary to clarify the relevant responsibilities of governments at all levels in order to build a scientific and perfect education public service system.

III. Concluding remarks

To sum up, we can see that in order to promote the sustainable development of art education, we must innovate according to local conditions, build a scientific and perfect public service system for art education, give full play to the leading role of the government, and effectively strengthen the effective integration of social forces, which will help improve the development level of art education and promote sustainable economic development.

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